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Once Upon A Time

It's a vast, vast midnight when my dreams started to play.
Once upon a time, perhaps I wouldn't want to stay.
A murky depiction of what awaits made me catch my breath.
Then a sudden flashback of memories, I once buried to death.

It's a dark, dark room that I can even feel my blindness.
Not a single light I see, but I'm certain it's a fortress.
Then I felt this warmth from someone's presence, that led me to a path
Step by step the way gets clear, bringing back my sight.

Finally, I saw this pal, whom I further called my 'friend'.
Almost 'best' we have become, how I wish this not to never end.
Brotherhood tied us together amongst those people in wilderness.
Insouciantly thinking not of them, exaltingly living each glance of
togetherness.

With equanimity I saw soundness in this edifice we started to build.
Founding it as tight as Eiffel, we've started to harvest the yield.
But at the midst of our journey, an excruciating roar from the field.
Again, this feeling of worry, has been cracking down our shield.

Every second I was thinking, enough could never be enough.
The world is cruel, and I'm feeling you've becoming cold and tough.
Reasons, perhaps, could clarify my thoughts, but you never say a word.
Now seclusion quivered us over, like we've sundered by the world.

'Till now I can't get over that even choices nothing has left.
I'm untying the knot of friendship, but I promise for the rope to be kept.
Thankful still for that single chance, though we ended up in strife.
'Cause even for once upon a time, you came and lighted up my life.